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Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy for Electrode Process Evaluation: Lithium Titanium Phosphate in Concentrated Aqueous Electrolyte

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Aqueous electrolytes in the form of highly concentrated solutions stand as a viable alternative to the organic counterpart as battery electrolytes thanks to the low flammability, toxicity, cost and large availability, while keeping good potential windows. In this work, a half-cell constituted of lithium titanium phosphate in a binary aqueous solution of sodium acetate (7 mol kg⁻¹) and potassium acetate (20 mol kg⁻¹) as a promising anode for sodium-ion batteries is characterized with constant current, static and dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy to reveal its thermodynamic and kinetic

properties. The experiments permit to withdraw some information on the thermodynamics (activation energy of processes) and kinetics (processes' parameters evolution) of the system. Physical information was extracted from impedance spectra with mathematical regression of a porous electrode intercalation model available in literature using an innovative procedure of batch-fitting of a complete set of spectra at once. The advantage and shortcoming on using impedance in battery development is discussed.

Introduction

Driven by the unique benefits of inherent safety, low cost, electrochemical stability, high ionic conductivity and environmental friendliness, super-concentrated aqueous electrolytes are receiving great interest in defining new chemistries for batteries.^[1] Although conventional lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) employing organic electrolytes have reached an acceptable performance limit, they still suffer from serious issues, such as safety and cost. Organic carbonate electrolytes used in conventional Li-ion batteries show low flashpoints, high melting points and high viscosities making them unsuitable for low-temperature applications.^[2] Moreover, conventional Li-ion batteries mostly rely on thermally unstable LiPF₆ which, in the presence

of moisture, can undergo degradation, producing HF and causing corrosion of battery components.^[3] An interesting alternative is the use of non-flammable, less toxic and cost-effective aqueous electrolytes. However, a major limitation in their use is the extremely narrow thermodynamic electrochemical stability window (ESW) of water (1.23 V). The ESW can be kinetically extended up to 1.5 V using diluted salt solutions, though such aqueous systems cannot compete with their organic counterparts in terms of energy density.^[4] To widen the ESW of aqueous electrolytes, researchers ventured into high concentration regimes. As early as in 1985, McKinnon and Dahn reported a saturated LiAsF₆ solution in propylene carbonate (PC) demonstrating an unusual intercalation behaviour that could not be possible in ordinary 1 M electrolytes.^[5] Curiously, the earlier attempts to breach the concentration restraint were performed with polymer electrolytes, giving origin to the "Polymer-in-Salt" concept.^[6] When in water, super-concentrated solutions of salts are called "Water-in-Salt" electrolytes (WISE), firstly developed by Suo et al., by dissolving lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide in water up to 21 mol kg⁻¹, enabling a voltage window of 3 V.^[1,7] The reason for this enhanced ESW stems from the low activity of water molecules at such high concentration, where the ions outnumber the water molecules that are incorporated into the solvation shells.^[8] In the high concentration scenario, water molecules form clusters in the sub-nanometre range, strongly interacting with one or more ions, resulting in large kinetic overpotentials for the electrolysis of water.^[9] Wider ESW electrolytes employ per-fluorinated sulfonyl imide salts such as lithium (fluorosulfonyl)(trifluoromethane sulfonyl)imide (FTFSI),^[10] lithium (pentafluoroethane sulfonyl)(trifluoromethane sulfonyl)imide (PTFSI), (LiTFSI),^[11] sodium trifluoromethanesulfonate (NaOTf),^[12] sodium

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bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (NaFSI)^[13] and potassium trifluoromethanesulfonate (KOTF).^[14]

Despite the outstanding improvements in the ESW, the environmental and economic concerns related to the use of fluorinated salts remain unresolved. In particular, LiTFSI, which is widely used in LIBs, exhibits severe oral and dermal toxicity, skin issues and can cause chronic aquatic toxicity.^[8] Furthermore, the limited availability and very high cost of these fluorinated salts practically nullify the advantages brought by super-concentration, making the practical implementation of WISE in energy storage very challenging.^[15,16] Conversely, the main problem in selecting new formulations for WISE is the lack of suitable salts with enough solubility to satisfy the WISE condition. Examples of cost-effective, highly soluble, and widely available salts are LiCl, CH₃COONa (AcONa), and CH₃COOK (AcOK). In particular, AcOK has been recently investigated,^[17] proposed in potassium ion batteries (KIBs), and employed in supercapacitors.^[18] Moreover, AcOK can be coupled with Li, Na and Zn salts to achieve binary electrolytes with concentrations above 20 mol kg⁻¹.^[19] For instance, S. Chen et al. reported a mixed-cation electrolyte composed of 32 mol kg⁻¹ AcOK and 1 mol kg⁻¹ (CH₃COO)₂Zn allowing a (2.0 V) Zn–MnO₂ aqueous rechargeable cell.^[20] Another interesting report features a 32 mol kg⁻¹ AcOK with 7 mol kg⁻¹ CH₃COOLi electrolyte utilizing C–TiO₂ as anode and LiMnO₄ as a cathode.^[8]

In the design of secondary batteries, a critical issue is the choice of electrode materials to be used in such a highly concentrated environment. In this framework, Sodium (Na) Super Ionic CONductor (NASICON) compounds offer significant advantages due to their stable structure and large ionic channels with accessible sites for highly efficient ions insertion-extraction.^[21] Moreover, the very low solubility and the possibility to modify the intercalation potential by tuning the chemical composition, so matching the bounds of electrolyte ESW, make NASICON compounds an ideal choice as electrode materials.^[18] Among them, LiTi₂(PO₄)₃ (LTP), with a relatively low average operative potential (0 V vs RHE when Na⁺ is intercalating) and an achievable capacity of up to 100–110 mAhg⁻¹ in aqueous electrolytes,^[22] can be considered of particular interest for use in WISE media. As already demonstrated in the literature, the low electrical conductivity of this NASICON phase requires a carbon shell around the active material particles to enable good electrochemical performances.^[22]

Taking advantage of the high solubility of AcOK, we investigated a binary system comprised of AcOK and AcONa, by keeping the AcOK concentration constant at 20 mol kg⁻¹, and increasing AcONa up to 7 mol kg⁻¹. A single composition (32 mol kg⁻¹ AcOK with 8 mol kg⁻¹ AcONa) was recently investigated as far as the electrochemical applications were concerned.^[23] In this paper, we performed a study on the electrical and electrochemical properties of the binary system, which are crucial to correctly address its application in batteries. To prove the advantages of using the most concentrated solution i.e., 7 mol kg⁻¹ AcONa with 20 mol kg⁻¹ AcOK as a WISE electrolyte, we studied the intercalation process of sodium ions using carbon-coated LiTi₂(PO₄)₃ (CLTP) NASICON as an electrode material. The electrochemical measurements include a kinetic

analysis through impedance spectroscopy as a function of the temperature. Moreover, dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (DEIS) was used to get further insights about the WISE/LTP interface during cycling. DEIS is an evolution of the classical Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy based on two principles of operation: i) all the frequencies to stimulate are injected at the same time in the system through a multi-sine wave; ii) system is drifted outside the equilibrium through a constant current, voltage or sweeping voltage.^[24] Oscillating voltage and current signals are sampled and the time-varying impedance is computed through Fourier analysis. This technique has been already proven to be of interest for electrochemical energy storage systems^[25] and materials.^[26] Despite being firstly introduced in the seventies, DEIS is not yet a widespread technique in routine laboratory analysis due to its inherent complexity. The interpretation of impedance data has also contributed to keep it out of many research groups. In fact, the remarkable capability of qualifying and quantifying physical processes happening in parallel or in series at the electrode/electrolyte interface requires the hard task of developing a proper physical model. In this work, we propose an approach to impedance data handling from measurement validation to careful model selection and regression. The used model was selected from the literature, proven to work for porous electrode undergoing ionic intercalation.^[26] The thrilling perspective of employing impedance spectroscopy in material research and the main shortcoming still to face are discussed.

Methods

Synthesis of materials and cell assembly

Carbon-coated LiTi₂(PO₄)₃ NASICON, (CLTP) was synthesized using a facile one-pot synthesis route. 1.78 g of phosphate precursor NH₄H₂(PO₄)₃ were dissolved in 40 mL of ethanol via stirring followed by the addition 3.51 g of Ti(OC₄H₉)₄ until complete dissolution. As lithium and carbon sources, 0.52 g of CH₃COOLi·2H₂O, and 0.58 g of D-(+)-Glucose, were added. The mixture was stirred for 4 h at 55 °C in a sealed container, then ethanol was evaporated at 80 °C with opened container obtaining a gel, which was dried under vacuum at 100 °C and finely ground with mortar and pestle. The obtained powder was calcined at 800 °C for 6 h under argon flux in a tubular furnace with ramp rate of 5 °C per minute and the gas flow of 50 mL per minute.

High concentration aqueous binary electrolyte was prepared mixing 20 mol kg⁻¹ potassium acetate (AcOK) with 7 mol kg⁻¹ sodium acetate (AcONa) dissolving AcOK (99%, Alfa Aesar) and AcONa (99%, Alfa Aesar) in high-quality Milli-Q water ($\sigma = 6.7 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) under sonication. The two concentrations, expressed in molality, are referred to the same amount of water. The final solution, 7 M AcONa + 20 M AcOK, will be labelled 7N20K hereafter. Also, a solution 1 M of AcONa was prepared to highlight the performance of the concentrated solution in comparison. All the electrolytes were stored and used at room conditions.

Slurries of active materials, PVDF (6020 by Solvay) binder and carbon black (Super P from Erachem Comilog, Inc.) in weight ratio 8:1:1 were prepared using anhydrous N-Methyl-2-Pyrrolidone (Merck) as the solvent. To avoid possible corrosion problems, the electrodes were prepared by dip-coating carbon cloth current

collectors in the slurries of active material for a loading of approximately 6 mg cm^{-2} . All measurement in aqueous electrolyte were conducted in a three-electrode glass cell with platinum mesh as counter electrode and a double junction Ag/AgCl electrode as reference.

For the comparative study of the intercalation of Li, Na and K ions commercial organic electrolytes were used due to the reactivity of Li in water: 1.0 M LiPF_6 in EC/DMC (LP30, Merck), 1 M NaClO_4 (Merck) in PC/FEC and 0.8 M KPF_6 (Merck) in EC/DEC. For the measurements in organic electrolytes, the slurries were casted on metal foils and CR2032 coin cells were assembled in an argon-filled glovebox ($[\text{O}_2] < 0.1 \text{ ppm}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}] < 0.1 \text{ ppm}$) using alkaline metal foils (Li, Na, K) as the counter electrodes. The active material loads were 2.4 mg cm^{-2} , 2.7 mg cm^{-2} and 1.7 mg cm^{-2} for Li, Na and K based cells respectively.

Conductivity measurement

The conductivity measurements were performed using Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) employing a dedicated dip probe cell with two platinum foils in a glass casing, with a cell factor of 1.04 cm^{-1} . Impedance spectra were recorded in a frequency range of 1 Hz to 200 kHz with an amplitude of 25 mV. All the samples were first degassed bubbling nitrogen in the electrolyte and the gas flux was kept during the whole measurement. A full spectra was acquired for a set of temperature ranging from 5°C to 70°C using a dedicated climatic chamber (Angelantoni). For all the samples, the bulk Ohmic resistance was recorded via the x-axis intercept at high frequency of the impedance spectra represented in a Nyquist plots.

Electrochemical rate tests

C-rate test was performed on the CLTP/7N20K system using the Galvanostatic Cycling with Potential Limitation (GCPL) protocol between 0.5 and -0.1 V vs RHE with the values 0.1 C, 0.5 C, 1 C, 5 C, 10 C and 0.1 C (10 cycles each). To underline the effect of the sodium concentration on the specific capacity and Coulombic efficiency, the same test was also performed with a dilute solution 1 M of sodium acetate. In the C-rate calculation, 1 C value corresponds to 136 mA g^{-1} considering the insertion and de-insertion of two alkaline ions into the structure.

Dynamic EIS

To perform DEIS experiments, an in-house built was used. It is constituted of three devices: a galvanostat/potentiostat (BioLogic SP-300), an arbitrary waveform generator (Keysight TruForm 33522B) and a digital oscilloscope (PicoTech PicoScope 4000a 8 channels). The connection between the instruments is schematically reported in Figure 1. While the potentiostat provides the main drift, the multisine is generated by the waveform generator and superimposed to the main signal. Current and voltage are sampled with the digital oscilloscope at high frequency through the auxiliary output of the potentiostat.

In this work a multi-sine wave from 100 mHz to 10 kHz was used in both galvanostatic with 1 C current (138 mA g^{-1}) and sweep-voltage drifting with a scan rate of 0.8 mV s^{-1} using the mentioned values, the two measurements last approximately the same time. All the frequencies in the multisine are integer multiples of the lower frequencies and they are not linear combination of at least four other frequencies to avoid intermodulation. The cell was kept in a Faraday's cage for all the DEIS measurements. The time-varying impedance computation was performed with the Dynamic Multi-

Figure 1. Schematic of the set-up for dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy.

Frequency Analyses (DMFA).^[24] Details on the techniques characteristics, how to choose the parameters, hardware components and software where discussed in depth in a previous publication.^[25]

Equivalent circuit model

To extract physical parameters from impedance spectra, a physical-based impedance model for intercalation reaction in a porous electrode^[26] was regressed on the experimental data. The graphical representation of the equivalent circuit model is shown in Figure 2.

It derives from the simplified transmission line model (TLM) for porous electrodes based on de Levie's theory for porous electrodes^[27] and describes a two-step reversible insertion process. The total impedance Z_T is given by Equation (1):

$$Z_T = R_s + R_p \left(\frac{\coth(kl)}{kl} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where is R_s the uncompensated solution resistance, R_p is the resistance of the entire pore, and it is a combination of the resistance of the solution in the pores (ρ_p) and the resistance of the solid particles (ρ_s).^[28] l is the pore thickness and k is a dimensionless parameter. Together kl denotes the impedance of single reacting sites.

Validation of impedance spectra

To validate the experimental data using the Kramers-Kronig transform (KKT) without compromising the inherent assumptions of steady state, we used a similar approach used by Sadkowski.^[29] This approach requires fitting the experimental data with a generalized measurement model and examining the simulated data's Kramers-Kronig (KK) transformability. The generalized measurement model used in the study is Padé approximants that are rational polynomials of the form of Equation (2):

$$Y(x) = \frac{a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0}{b_m x^m + b_{m-1} x^{m-1} + \dots + b_m x + 1} \quad (2)$$

Where $Y(x)$ represents the complex admittance, n and m are the orders of the denominator and numerator polynomials respectively;

Figure 2. Equivalent circuit representation of the physical model for intercalation reaction in a porous electrode.

$x = \sqrt{j\omega}$ with j being the imaginary unit and ω the angular frequency. a_i and b_i are the coefficients of the rational polynomial which must be real in order to be able to make a complex non-linear fit.

The experimental data was fitted with the rational polynomial from degree four up to eight for spectra obtained under constant current, and from degree four up to nine for data obtained under constant voltage. As shown in a previous publication,^[30] the Akaike information criterion (AIC) was used to constrain the complexity of the polynomials. For the constant current data, the minimum AIC was obtained for a rational polynomial of order six while for the constant voltage data, a minimum AIC was obtained for a rational polynomial of order eight. In both cases, the rational polynomial obtained at the minimum AIC fully represented the system, and the fits produced reproduced all regions of the spectrum quite well.

Next, conducted a KKT on the fit/simulated spectra generated from the regression of the rational polynomials. The KKT test used in the paper is the Lin-KK method by Schönleber^[31] (as implemented in the Impedancepy^[32]). The KKT tests were done using the impedance instead of the admittance for compatibility with the package used for the analysis (described in the next section).

Model regression methods

To extract the parameters of the equivalent circuit model, we used a multi-variate complex nonlinear optimization approach (provided by the Pymultipleis Python package, GitHub link: <https://github.com/richinex/pymultipleis>) to regress the equivalent circuit model to the measured data. The parameter estimation was of the form of Equation (3):

$$\hat{p} = \min_p (p) \quad (3)$$

where p is the vector of parameters to fit and l is the loss function³³. The loss function χ_T^2 , which was minimized during the complex nonlinear optimization, is a sum of two terms given by Equation (4):

$$\chi_T^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \chi_i^2 \sum_{n=1}^{N_p} \left(s_n \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \left(\frac{\partial p_{n,i}}{\partial i} \right)^2 \right) \quad (4)$$

The first term χ_T^2 on the right hand side of Equation (4) is the scaled version of the chi-square represented as Equation (5):

$$\chi^2 = \sum_k^{N_f} w_k \left(\left(Z_{Re,k} - \hat{Z}_{Re}(p) \right)^2 + \left(Z_{Im,k} - \hat{Z}_{Im}(p) \right)^2 \right) \quad (5)$$

Where N_f , Z_k , \hat{Z}_k , w_k , P , Z_{Re} , Z_{Im} represent the number of data points (frequencies measured), the k^{th} value of the experimental impedance, the k^{th} value of the calculated impedance, the weight associated with the k^{th} frequency, the model parameter and the real and imaginary impedances.

The second term of Equation (4) comprises two sub terms, S_a vector containing values that control the parameters' degree of smoothness and the squared second derivative of the parameters with respect to the impedance index i .

Pymultipleis considers several impedance spectra at once during the fitting process and thus allows a certain form of dependence to be observed between the optimal parameters and the control variable being analysed. The fitting was done in two stages. First, arbitrary initial guesses were used with the stochastic option of pymultipleis. Here, the parameter S , also known as the smoothing factor, is set to one. After running an initial fit, more reliable initial values for the model were obtained. These prefit values were then used in a second-stage minimization where the smoothing factor is set to zero; in this case the loss function becomes equivalent to a scaled version of the chi-square.

Results and Discussion

Binary electrolyte characterization

To understand the thermodynamics of intercalation of lithium, sodium and potassium in CLTP a first experiment was performed with organic solvents for their wide stability window. In Figure 3 is reported the first cycle for the three coin-cells based on the three metal ions.

As it is possible to observe, apart from differences in the specific capacity (129, 113, and 92 mAhg⁻¹ in LiPF₆, NaPF₆, and KPF₆ respectively), Li⁺ and Na⁺ have insertion potentials that are quite close while the insertion of potassium into the structure needs an extra reducing potential of about 0.9 V. This can be interpreted as a higher energy required to introduce and accommodate the larger K⁺ ion into the crystalline structure. The experiment suggests that in a Na⁺/K⁺ mixed

Figure 3. Reduction profile of carbon-coated lithium titanium phosphate in organic electrolytes containing lithium (red curve), sodium (blue curve) and potassium (green curve) ions. Tested in coin cell against a strip of the corresponding metal.

electrolyte, the Na^+ ions will be preferentially intercalated in the anode.

Thanks to the good conductivity, broad ESW of WISE, and the large concentration of alkaline cations, the 7N20K was selected for the following study of the CLTP interface for sodium ion batteries.

Not only the operating voltage is important for battery application but also the electrolyte conductivity to support high C-rates. The results of the conductivity test for the electrolyte with higher is reported in Figure 4.

All the compositions follow Vogel-Tamman-Fulcher (VTF) behaviour [Eq. (6)]:

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 e^{-\frac{E_a}{k_B(T-T_0)}} \quad (6)$$

Figure 4. Conductivity of high concentrated binary solution of sodium acetate (7 M) and potassium acetate (20 M) at different temperatures; measured in deep probe cell.

Here E_{pa} is a pseudo-activation energy for ions transport, K_b represents the Boltzmann's constant, T is the absolute temperature and T_0 can be interpreted as the ideal glass transition temperature. The ionic conductivity decreases with increasing the electrolyte concentration as expected in highly concentrated electrolytes. All the sodium containing samples, indeed, show values lower or nearly equal to that of 20 M AcOK,^[17] however the 7N20K concentration still exhibits a good value of conductivity i.e., 21.2 mS cm^{-1} at 25°C , good enough for battery purposes. Here, the available water molecules cannot effectively shell the respective cations, promoting the interaction of anions (AcO^- in this case) with the cations without causing any significant re-association resulting in the modification of the local hydrogen bonding.^[8]

Electrochemical performance of the material

Electrochemical rate test results are shown in Figure 5.

The experiment demonstrates that the performances in the WISE electrolyte are clearly better than those in the diluted solution in terms of specific capacity and efficiency. In particular, the cathodic and anodic capacities are 104 and 84 mAh g^{-1} , (80% charge efficiency) at the first cycle in 7N20K, while in the diluted solution the values decrease to 96 and 36 mAh g^{-1} (40% efficiency), respectively. Moreover, when cycled in the WISE electrolyte at 1 C the CLTP is capable to provide an average anodic specific capacity of 68 mAh g^{-1} with an average charge efficiency of 99.0%. At the end of the test (60 cycles), the CLTP/WISE interface shows a capacity retention of 90%.

The potential profiles, reported in Figure 6, match the sodium intercalation as performed in organic electrolyte (two plateaus) despite its concentration being 2.85 times lower than the one of potassium confirming the thermodynamic preference of sodium intercalation. The comparison with the 1st and

Figure 5. C-rate test of half-cell lithium titanium phosphate in high concentrated binary electrolyte (blue dots) and diluted sodium acetate (red dots) as comparison.

Figure 6. Charge/discharge profiles of CLTP in concentrated binary electrolyte 7N20K (upper plot) and diluted sodium acetate solution (bottom plot). 1st and 10th cycle at 0.1 C current are reported as comparison.

10th cycles for high and low concentration of sodium shows the weaker performance of the latter.

Temperature dependence of static EIS and parameters trend

The thermodynamic of CLTP/7N20K interface was studied with EIS at different temperatures from 20 °C to 70 °C using physical model regression to extract the system parameters and looking at their temperature dependency. EIS spectra were recorded in a frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 100 kHz with an amplitude of 50 mV under N₂ bubbling in a flooded three electrode cell. The material was reduced until a potential value in the middle of the lower plateau to represent at best the intercalation reaction. To avoid any interference from the surrounding, all the impedance measurements were carried out in a Faraday cage inside the climatic chamber. It is possible to observe from Figure 7a double effect of the temperature on the interface itself: first of all, the resistances, both the electrolyte one and the charge transfer one (that of the semicircle) decreases. On the other hand, the Warburg coefficient (i.e. steepness of the linear part at low frequency) increases.

At first a simple geometrical analysis of the impedance spectra was performed, resulting already in a few interesting findings. The charge transfer resistance was evaluated as the intercept of the linear part of the impedance with the x-axis

Figure 7. Series of EIS measurement taken at different temperatures on a three-electrode glass cell of CLTP/7N20K.

(real part of the impedance at the end of the semicircle) and subtracting the electrolyte contribution, i.e., the high frequency intercept of the charge transfer arc. The activation energy of the charge transfer was calculated using the empirical Arrhenius Equation (7):

$$R_{CT} = R_{CT,0} e^{\frac{E_a}{RT}} \quad (7)$$

where $R_{CT,0}$ is the charge transfer resistance at infinite temperature, and E_a the activation energy. Figure 8 shows the Arrhenius plot of the charge transfer resistance. The low activation energy (0.12 eV or 11.58 kJ mol⁻¹), in line with that of other electrode/aqueous electrolyte systems,^[34,35] proves the very good kinetic properties of the interface between the NASICON electrode and the highly concentrated electrolyte. In particular, charge transfer resistance between liquid electrolyte and electrode is mainly affected by two contributes: the desolvation step and the diffusion in the Solid Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) step.^[36] Both this contributes are expected to be low in water-in-salt electrolytes due to the low number of water molecules that can form a hydration shell and the absence of a proper SEI.

The diffusion coefficient is calculated via Equation (8):

Figure 8. Arrhenius plot of charge transfer resistance for CLTP in 7N20K.

Figure 9. a) Evaluation of the diffusion coefficient of alkaline ions inside LTP structure. Linear relationship between Z' and $\omega^{-1/2}$ in the diffusion-controlled region of the impedance (low frequencies); b) Arrhenius plot of the diffusion coefficient.

$$D_{A^+} = \left(\frac{RT}{\sqrt{2}n^2F^2C\sigma_w} \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

where R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, A is the surface area of the electrode, n is the number of mobile ions inside the structure (evaluated to be 1.7 in the case of the impedance measurements), F is the Faraday's constant (96485 C mol^{-1}), C is the concentration of the mobile ions inside the electrode structure (volume considered to be constant, concentration value 12930 mol m^{-3}) and σ_w is the Warburg coefficient. Figure 9a shows the linear relationship between the real part of the impedance and $\omega^{-1/2}$. The slope of the lines is in fact the Warburg coefficient, which is used in the previous formula to obtain the diffusion coefficient. As shown in Figure 9b the diffusion coefficient follows the Arrhenius relationship.

The value of the diffusion coefficient D at room temperature (around $10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is in line with other reports in the literature.^[37] Also, it is noteworthy that the aqueous electrolyte improves the diffusion of alkaline ions inside the electrode structure, as previously reported.^[38] Moreover, the low activation energy value (0.48 eV) suggests that the diffusion can be easily improved by increasing the temperature.

Dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

For both galvanostatic and sweep-voltage experiments, two cycles of DEIS were collected starting from the electrode in the complete oxidized state (0.8 V vs RHE). The drift curves computed with DMFA (1 s resolution) are reported in Figure 10.

Figure 10. a) Voltammogram and b) voltage profile extracted with DMFA after DEIS experiment during sweep-voltammetry and galvanostatic, respectively.

In Figure 11 is reported the DMFA extraction for a full cycle (reduction and then oxidation) of both experiment with a 3D and 2D representation of the time-varying impedance (10 s resolution). A few observations can be made on the shape of the impedance spectra in different points of the potential. The

Figure 11. Results of the DMFA for a reduction/oxidation cycle in galvanostatic and voltammetry experiment. The three rows, labelled on the left, reports the drift reconstruction (a–d) and the time-varying impedance in both 3D (e–h) and 2D (i–l) views to best appreciate the changes in the shape. The first two columns represent the galvanostatic experiment, divided in reduction and oxidation, while the last two the cyclic voltammetry divided with the same criterion.

first and bigger remarks is how different the impedance spectra for the two experiments at the potential of the redox semi-reaction (lower potential plateau). After the peak in the voltammogram the impedance at any frequency significantly increases in magnitude (see the blue spectra in the picture) as a sign of strong mass diffusion control. On the contrary, in a galvanostatic experiment the kinetics of the reaction is fixed from the current flowing and the impedance spectra maintain the same shape during the plateau of potential.

Another interesting observation in the galvanostatic DEIS experiment is the different shapes of the spectra during reduction and oxidation in the same plateau. In reduction, the first semicircle is less depressed, and the diffusion tail is better defined (see 2D plot in Figure 11).

After the acquisition, the DEIS spectra were validated and was found an error between the experimental and Kramers-Krönig-transformed data in both the galvanostatic and sweep-voltage cases less than 0.4% of the magnitude of the impedance; the complete discussion is reported in the supporting information.

The following step was to regress the physical model described in the Validation of impedance spectra section to the measured data. To evaluate the quality of the fitting two principles were considered: i) the value of the AIC (discussed in the Model regression methods section) and ii) the relative error

of the parameters, obtained from the covariance matrix. Even a good fitting in term of χ^2 and a graphical inspection may be physically inappropriate while mathematically correct so it is important to stick to the two principles listed above. It was first noticed that the Warburg coefficient and time constant of the finite-space Warburg were interdependent (large absolute error). The two parameters were then removed in favour of a simple capacitor; the results are reported in Figure 12 and Figure 13. The physical interpretation for the need of an element substitution in the circuit to better describe the processes can be the following: the diffusion coefficient is large and so the time constant is small; it is possible that the process is not visible in the relatively low explored frequency band or that another process is predominant in the same time scale. The capacitance can represent the Faradic pseudocapacitance due to the finite volume of the pores. Unfortunately, the large relative error of Q_h element of the CPE suggests that the model is not yet correct even though appears very good in Figure 13b and Figure 13f.

The second important point to make is that the model, even the original non-simplified, is not sophisticated enough to represent the DEIS during sweep-voltammetry (fitted data doesn't match the measured one). It can be possible to see the need of more elements to describe it from the data validation

Figure 12. Results of the mathematical regression of the physical model on DEIS galvanostatic. Only interesting spectra are reported where the shape changes significantly. The respective voltage is indicated.

in supporting information; the minimum Padé order to fit the data is greater than the case of the galvanostatic experiment.

The asymmetry of the impedance spectra acquired during reduction and oxidation can be described in view of the time-varying parameters obtained by the fitting of the impedance spectra themselves (see Figure 13). Two main observations arise: i) significant changes in the parameter value happen during phase transition and when the current changes sign from reduction to oxidation; ii) some parameters are asymmetric with respect to the reduction/oxidation.

The three main processes involved in the reaction are the diffusion of the ions towards the interface, the adsorption of the ion on the Inner Helmholtz Plane and the ion intercalation in the lattice of the active material. The resistances associated to these steps are represented in the model with R_p , R_{ad} and R_{int} respectively. R_p and R_{int} , as reported in Figure 13g and 13 h, are largely symmetric with respect to reduction (intercalation) and oxidation (deintercalation) while R_{ad} is asymmetric; in particular, this parameter is three times higher during the oxidation (averagely 9 Ω) than during the reduction (averagely around 3 Ω) (Figure 13d). The presence of an asymmetry on the process of adsorption has already been reported in literature for Li^+ in organic electrolytes using pulsed current techniques^[39] (namely “Laplace transform impedance method”). The role of the adsorption process and its thermodynamics is under extensive study from both experimental and computational perspective and it has been reported,^[40–43] that the solvation/desolvation step in the case of different ions is limiting the insertion in layered structures, especially at low temperatures.^[44] The thermodynamic reason for this asymmetry has been attributed to the difference in Gibbs free energy of the ion in solid state and solvated.^[39,45]

From the kinetics point of view, our hypothesis is that the asymmetry in adsorption resistance is due to a symmetry coefficient of the Butler-Volmer-like adsorption kinetics different than 0.5. From the ratio of R_{ad} during oxidation and reduction, a possible value of α equal to 0.75 can be calculated solving Equation (9):

$$\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \sim 3 \quad (9)$$

Extrapolating the Marcus theory for electron transfer to the adsorption process, this result would suggest that the adsorption kinetics is highly asymmetric, due to a strong difference in potential energy between adsorbed and desorbed ions; in particular, the potential energy of the desorbed ions should be lower than the one of the adsorbed ones. The authors are aware that such extrapolation is not adequately justified; however, no discussion on experimental kinetic data is available in the literature to the authors’ knowledge, due to the challenge of deconvoluting the adsorption step from the charge transfer one; a complete understanding of the kinetics requires a theoretical study at molecular level.

We have to add that another hypothesis correlates the asymmetry of R_{ad} to the different Na^+ concentration profile in the electrolyte close to the interface during oxidation and reduction,^[46] however, the dependence of the kinetics on the concentration of the desorbed ion in solution would suggest that R_{ad} should be lower during the oxidation than during the reduction.

Conclusion

Concentrated aqueous electrolytes have been identified as possible alternatives to organic carbonate solvents in alkaline secondary batteries thanks to the low safety risk, toxicity, and cost. However, an important limitation is the narrow potential stability window of water that can be overcome with high salt concentration. Among the many available salts, acetates were selected for its low cost and the already reported wide stability window. To investigate the possibilities of using the electrolyte in battery applications, a nano-carbon coated lithium titanium phosphate electrode was studied as a promising anode for sodium-ion batteries considered its low potential of intercalation for alkali metal, able to exploit the lower stability limit of

Figure 13. Time-varying parameters of DEIS galvanostatic experiment obtained from the regression of the simplified equivalent circuit model. The potential profile is reported in each figure to show the correlation with parameter change.

the selected electrolyte. Understanding the thermodynamics and kinetics of the electrode/electrolyte interface processes is crucial for the choice of the materials and fine-tuning the operational conditions, like current rates or potential limits.

In this work, an electrochemical characterization of lithium titanium phosphate porous electrode covered with carbon nanoparticles in highly concentrated binary electrolyte of sodium

and potassium acetate was characterized in half-cell configuration as a promising anode for sodium-ion batteries.

An initial series of experiments in organic electrolytes containing lithium, sodium and potassium ions suggested that the sodium intercalation in lithium titanium phosphate would be preferential than potassium in the explored potential interval. The conductivity of the chosen highly concentrated electrolyte was measured to be 20 mS cm^{-1} at room temper-

ature that is enough to guarantee currents up to 5 C in the cell. A c-rate test was performed from 0.1 C to 10 C resulting in a good Coulombic efficiency of 90 % after the 60th cycle.

Static impedance was then used in experiments at different temperatures to measure the activation energy of ion diffusion and charge transfer process.

Finally, two dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy experiments were performed in the cases of constant current and sweep-voltage drift. It takes just a visual inspection of the time-varying impedance plotted in three dimension to appreciate the enormous difference in the kinetics for the two types of drift. The authors conclude that in the case of material for battery application the constant current dynamic impedance experiment is preferable to study the system under a constant kinetics. Employing a physical model for the impedance from the literature, time-varying physical parameters were extracted and used to comment the asymmetry in the impedance spectra during reduction and oxidation. Unfortunately, the model proven to be insufficient to fully describe the system and trust the numerical values obtained. Nonetheless, an idea on how powerful DEIS can be to study and optimize materials or cells configurations were discussed. The time-varying parameters indicates which process are affected by the drifting and how. With a proper physical model in hand, this approach can be applied to different c-rates or electrolytes to understand the effect on the performances from another prospects.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: aqueous electrolyte · dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy · equivalent circuit model · lithium titanium phosphate · sodium-ion battery

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